

**A Study on Identification of Auditory, Visual and
Kinaesthetic Learning Essentials for Adolescents Studying in
Government Schools at Dakshina Kannada District**

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INTRODUCTION

Active thinking and logical reasoning are highly valued capabilities of individuals. By adopting specific learning exercises as a deliberate part of one's classroom learning, learners can increase their ability to integrate logical and creative thinking patterns which generate more productive and innovative thinking with maximized academic performance among students. Cognition tells us the processing of the information that is received through the senses. Learning is a brain-based process that is a mental activity associated with thought, logical reasoning, language, and other specific mental processes. Active academic learning in the classroom requires a high and sustained intellectual capacity for each individual. Each learner is different in her/his learning capacity and some are good in observation, some in hearing, and some learn better by doing. However, a specialized approach in classroom teaching enhances the learning efficiency among the students. In this student population, some are habitually more interested in learning by doing, some by seeing, and some by listening. However, when we look into government-run school classrooms and teaching methods, they are not preferred or specialized by considering or recognizing the learning heterogeneity among the student population. In India, most of the teachers are not well equipped and adequately trained. If any improvement or reform is to be effected in teaching, the first preference is to improve the quality of the teachers. It is also important to make the teacher aware of the importance of learner-oriented teaching activities in the classroom. It is foremost important for teachers to focus on student's preferred learning styles.

LEARNING ESSENTIALS

Classifying student's learning styles and understanding their learning essentials can benefit both students and teachers in making the best academic output. As students learn in their learning ways. So, teachers can modify their teaching style, which is more consistent with students learning styles.

Identifying such strengths and empowering the students for optimal use of such potentiality to improve their academic performance is an important responsibility of all educational professionals.

"Learning Style" is a sensory pathway or modality through which students find the easiest ways to learn and strengthen their memory. It will also include a complete profile of how a student performs as a learner. Some are auditory learners and some learn better through the visual method and few learners are kinesthetic learners who need a bodily movement. Every student is different in reading, writing, comprehension, and logical reasoning. Based on the intellectual capacity, the student will pursue learning in the classroom. Normally, classrooms are not specified for any particular category of learners. The classroom includes all the types of students who will not be good in any one particular learning process.

Auditory Learning Style

Auditory learning is a method of learning through hearing. These types of learners learn effectively in the auditory style and receive information through the auditory organs. These individuals store information through listening and interpreting, understand by using pitch, rhythm, emphasis, and speed of speaking. This type of learner will also gain knowledge from reading out loud, repetitive hearing of the same sound, discussion with friends, etc.

Visual Learning Style

Visual learners think in pictures and learn best in visual images. These types of learners depend on the instructor's or facilitator's non-verbal expressions such as body language. They also take descriptive notes on the material being presented. The school curriculum can be improved by the use of a greater variety of teaching methods based on the diversity of learning styles among students. The use of original art can influence the students to have maximized improvement in their academic performance.

Kinesthetic Learning Style

Kinesthetic learning is a learning method in which better improvement in learning takes place through carrying out physical activities in the teaching process rather than lectures or watching demonstrations. Individuals with a kinesthetic learning style are comfortable with an active "hands-on" teaching approach. These learners prefer and enjoy the interaction with the physical

world. Some students learn better through experiences by involving in activities or learning by doing.

A review of literature has revealed that the present teaching approach in the classroom is "teachers centered" the "lecture method" is one of the commonly used teaching approaches. In addition, these studies also indicated that the "teachers are not effectively trained" to use teaching-learning aids. The traditional method of teaching is ineffective to influence students for better academic performance and it does not match the student's preferred learning style. The present study is identified the specific teaching approach in government secondary schools against auditory, visual, and kinaesthetic learning styles of the students. Since there is no similar argument for identifying a specific learning style that dominates other types of learning styles to improve student's academic performance, this study is very important to identify either students prefer auditory learning style, visual learning style, or kinaesthetic learning style for their flexible learning experience. It is also observed that none of the studies identified auditory, visual, and kinaesthetic learning essentials of the students this study is indicating the specific method of learning that is preferred by students with specific learning styles. Even, none of the studies been identified that the specific teaching strategy or strategies that will suit student's preferred learning styles. The present study is unique among all studies which identify the effective teaching approach or approaches that will match and fulfill the auditory, visual, and kinaesthetic learning styles of the students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted based on the following objectives.

- (i) To identify the socio-demographic profile of the respondents.
- (ii) To identify the various teaching approaches by teachers in government schools.
- (iii) To identify the learning style of the adolescents.
- (iv) To identify the learning essentials of adolescents in classroom learning.
- (v) To identify and suggest an effective contribution (from various stakeholders) for better teaching and learning.

METHOD OF THE STUDY

The research design is exploratory cum descriptive in nature. The major emphasis of this study was to find the auditory, visual and kinesthetic learning essentials of the adolescents and suggest students, parents, educational professionals, and the government set up the appropriate curriculum design and teaching approach, which will match the student's learning style and provide education on student's learning essentials of preferred learning style.

Universe

The universe of the study means the geographical area selected for the study. The geographical area of the study consists of five taluks of Dakshina Kannada District in Karnataka state, namely, Bantwal, Beltangadi, Mangaluru, Puttur&Sulia.

Population

In this study, the population included all the students who belong to the age group between 12 years to 16 years. The selected students are studying in 8th, 9th, and 10th classes at Government Educational Institutions under Karnataka State Education Board in Dakshina Kannada District. The population size in this study is twelve thousand sixty-five (12065) students from one hundred and sixty-eight (168) secondary schools distributed in five Taluks of Dakshina Kannada District, such as Bantwal (36), Beltangadi (34), Mangaluru (59), Puttur (23) and Sulia (16).

Samples Selected for the Study

The researcher consulted the expert statistician to use statistical applications to decide the sample size. We have applied the below formula to calculate the sample size for this study. We have applied the below formula to calculate the sample size for this study.

Where N=Population

e = 0.05

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

With a 95% confidence level and 5% precision with a 1.5 design effect, the total sample size comes to be **592** (Therefore we have taken **600** as the sample size for this study) according to the formula given by Yamane, T. (1967).

Data Collection

The researcher visited 10 government secondary schools in five taluks of Dakshina Kannada District, such as Bantwal, Beltangadi, Mangaluru, Puttur, and Sulia with the permission given by the Deputy Director of Public Instruction, Dakshina Kannada District, Mangaluru. The researcher has also taken permission from respective heads in each school. The researcher with his research colleagues personally visited the classrooms and distributed the questionnaire to the students. The researcher has given a detailed introduction about research and clear instruction on the procedure of marking the responses. The researcher also collected some qualitative information from the respondents through the interview method. In the end, 600 questionnaires were collected after the student's responses.

Data Analysis

The researcher scored systematically by using an appropriate scoring key for the responses collected from the respondents. The data collected were consolidated for analysis and interpretation. The data gathered were converted into the data coding sheet and given appropriate scores. After scoring, the data were calculated and analyzed. First, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation for continuous variables, frequency, and percentage for categorical variables) was used to know the frequencies of the data. Second, a comparison test was conducted to know the differences between socio-demographic variables, teaching style, learning style, and learning essentials. Third, a coefficient correlation test (single-tailed) was also conducted to find the relationship between socio-demographic variables and teaching style, learning style, and learning essentials to understand the relationship between latent variables. The overall data analysis was done using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Version: 25).

INSTRUMENTS USED

This study used the following instruments for collecting required data.

1. Socio-Demographic Schedule (SDS) Developed by Researcher (2019).
2. Teaching Status Questionnaire (TSQ) Developed by Researcher (2019).
3. Learning Styles Survey (LSS) Developed by Andrew et al., (2002).

4. Learning Essentials Questionnaire (LEQ) Developed by Researcher (2019).

Development of Instruments

In a pilot study, the printed copy of the scales was given to thirty (Five percent of the total sample) secondary students studying in a government school of Bantwal Taluk. The students were randomly selected and given a questionnaire with clear instructions. The students were asked to respond to the items by choosing given options such as never, rarely, sometimes, often, and always. The maximum time taken by respondents to respond to the items was one hour. The collected data were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha and obtained above 0.7 reliability score.

The researcher constructed all four scales under the "Graphic Rating Scale method." scales were finalized with a consensus approach the items selected in the instruments are discussed with panel judges to understand whether they are appropriate and suitable to identify the present method of teaching, learning style and learning essentials in government secondary schools. Their opinion has been collected for the validation of the item. The items in the scales were modified, reconstructed, and rewritten on the suggestions offered by experts by removing three questions. With the little different opinions and suggestions given by the experts, the questions in the scale were once again modified, rewritten, and finalized. With the good advice of the experts, the scales were considered to be used in the final study for the data collection.

MAJOR FINDINGS

Demographic Findings

- A total of 600 adolescents in which male 272 (45.3%) and female 328 (54.6%) aged between 12 and 16 years studying in government secondary schools in Dakshina Kannada District were the respondents in this study.
- Most respondents (74.5%, n= 447) in this study belong to rural area in which are males 208 (72.8%), and females 239 (76.4%). 153 (25.5%) respondents belong to urban area in which 64 (23.5%) are males, and 89 (27.1%) females.
- As per the educational qualification of the respondents' parents, a majority (74.85%) is up to SSLC or below, and the rest (25.15%) are above SSLC.
- The majority of the respondent's fathers' (52.5%, n=315) are daily workers, and mothers (46.2%, n=277) are house makers.

- A significant majority of the respondent's (80.7%) annual family income is below Rs. 50,000/. Only 19.4 percent of families have above Rs. 50,000/-annual income.
- A majority of the respondents (43.5%, n=261) are in the 9th class with 141 males and 120 females. 211 (35.2%) respondents are in 10th class and 21.3 percent (n=128) in 8th class.
- The Kannada language is the predominant medium of instruction in schools with 92.8%, n=557.

Descriptive Statistic

Methods of Teaching, Learning Style, and Learning Essentials						
		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Method of Teaching	A visual method of teaching	600	7	32	16.85	4.415
	Auditory method of teaching	600	6	31	21.69	3.968
	Kinesthetic method of teaching	600	7	32	20.98	4.400
Learning Style	Visual learning style	600	9	38	25.03	4.711
	Auditory learning style	600	9	40	22.26	5.643
	Kinesthetic learning style	600	4	34	18.29	5.736
Learning Essentials	Visual learning essentials	600	9	40	28.13	6.148
	Auditory learning essentials	600	3	36	22.47	6.483
	Kinesthetic learning essentials	600	6	39	23.83	6.179

Comparison between Major Variables

Multiple Comparisons between Teaching Methods

- While comparing mean score of visual (16.85), auditory (21.69), and kinesthetic (20.98) methods of teaching, auditory ($p < 0.001$) and kinesthetic ($p < 0.001$) methods of teaching are found to be very highly significant than the visual method of teaching.
- The kinesthetic method of teaching ($p = 0.011$) is found to be significant comparing to the auditory method of teaching.

Multiple Comparisons between Learning Styles

- While comparing mean scores of learning styles such as visual learning (25.03), auditory learning (22.26), and kinesthetic learning (18.29), auditory (< 0.001) and kinesthetic (< 0.001) learning styles are very highly significant than visual learning style.

- Comparing kinesthetic learning style with auditory learning style, kinesthetic learning style (<0.001) is very highly significant.
- Even though the above result highlights the importance of kinesthetic learning style while comparing to visual and auditory learning style, the high mean difference ($I-J=6.742$) indicates visual learning style is very highly significant comparing to the other two learning styles.

Multiple Comparisons between Learning Essentials

- While comparing the mean score of learning essentials such as visual learning (28.13), auditory learning (22.47), and kinesthetic learning (23.83), auditory (<0.001), and kinesthetic (<0.001) learning essentials are found to be very highly significant than visual learning essentials.
- Kinesthetic learning essentials (<0.001) are highly significant compared to auditory learning essentials.
- Even though the result shows kinesthetic learning essentials are very highly significant comparing to visual and auditory learning essentials, the mean score indicates visual learning essentials are very highly significant compared to auditory and kinesthetic learning essentials.

Comparing the Learning Essentials with Age Group

- A very high significant association ($p<0.001$) is found between visual learning essentials and age group within 13 and 14 years (Mean=26.55).
- Auditory learning essentials are of high significance ($p<0.001$) with the age group between 15 and 16 years (Mean=24.00).
- A very high significant association ($p<0.001$) was also found between kinesthetic learning essentials and an (incomplete)

Comparing the Learning Style with Gender

- Association between visual learning style and female respondents (Mean=24.40) is very highly significant ($p<0.001$).
- Auditory learning style and female respondents (Mean=21.68) are found to be highly significant ($p=0.006$).

Comparing the Method of Teaching with Area of Residence

- The result shows a highly significant association ($p=0.006$) between the auditory method of teaching and rural area of residence (Mean=21.95).

- A very high significant association ($p < 0.001$) is also found between the kinesthetic method of teaching and rural area of residence (Mean=21.32).

Comparing the Learning Essentials with Respondent's Residence

- A significant association ($p = 0.016$) is found between visual learning essentials and rural areas of residence (Mean=28.49).
- Association between kinesthetic learning essentials and rural area of residence (Mean=24.17) is also found significantly correlated ($p = 0.002$).

Comparing the Learning Essentials with Family Annual Income

- Association between visual learning essentials and family annual income above 100,000 (Mean=28.79) has very high significance ($p < 0.001$).
- Association between auditory learning essentials and family income above 100,000 (Mean=24.88) is also found to be very high significant ($p < 0.001$).

Comparing the Learning Style with Class of Studying

- Auditory learning style is found to be highly significantly associated ($p = 0.009$) with the 10th class of studying (Mean=21.59).
- Association between kinesthetic learning style and class 10th (Mean=17.88) is found to be significant ($p = 0.023$).

Comparing the Learning Essentials with Class of Studying

- High significant association ($p = 0.004$) is identified between visual learning essentials and 10th class of studying (Mean=29.20).
- Association between auditory learning essentials and 10th class (Mean=23.56) of studying is found to be very highly significant ($p < 0.001$).
- High significant association ($p = 0.002$) is found between kinesthetic learning essentials and 10th class (Mean=25.04) of studying.

Correlation of the Major Variables

- There is a correlation ($r = 0.312$) between the visual method of teaching and the visual learning style.
- Correlation is also found between the visual method of teaching and visual learning essentials ($r = 0.270$).

- Our study also found a moderate level of correlation ($r=0.435$) between visual learning style and visual learning essentials.
- A correlation ($r=0.241$) is found between the auditory method of teaching and the auditory learning style.
- Correlation ($r=0.183$) is found between the auditory method of teaching and auditory learning essentials.
- A moderate level of correlation is also found between auditory learning style and auditory learning essentials ($r=0.411$).
- There is a correlation ($r=0.104$) between the kinesthetic method of teaching and the kinesthetic learning style.
- A correlation is found ($r=0.194$) between the kinesthetic method of teaching and kinesthetic learning essentials.
- The correlation ($r=0.308$) is also identified between kinesthetic learning style and kinesthetic learning essentials.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for the Students

- Use multi senses effectively in the learning process.
- Take multimedia support (computers, video and audio gadgets etc.) in learning process.
- Use various materials to learn through vision and touch.
- Have experiential learning.

Recommendations for the Teachers

- Prepare most suitable teaching module for transforming knowledge
- Use multimedia
- Use practical method
- Facilitate the students through students centered classroom teaching strategies

Recommendations for the Parents

- Facilitate student's learning by providing their learning essentials.
- Observe children's behaviour
- Participate in school activities
- Maintain continues communication with teachers

Recommendations for the School Administration

- Fulfill the various learning essentials
- Provide proper infrastructure
- Provide appropriate lab facilities
- Appoint expert teachers or expertize the teachers
- provide regular appropriate training to the teachers

Recommendations for the Board of Education

- Convert more verbal learning curriculum into experiential learning
- Adopt descriptive, oral and skill based assessment system
- Timely assess the policies, programs, and teaching learning modules
- Setup an effective curriculum plan considering visual, auditory and kinesthetic learners

Recommendations for the Government

- Provide effective education at the grass root level
- Encourage and support researches on various aspects of teaching and learning
- Provide appropriate teaching-learning technologies and maintain quality laboratories
- Improve the financial condition of the rural families
- Appoint full time or part time mental health professionals in government schools

Recommendations for the Voluntary Organizations

- Provide special education
- Donate teaching and learning equipment
- Conduct research
- Set up a community study center in their villages
- Organize various educational and awareness programs
- Recognize and honor students

RESEARCH IMPLICATION

The key findings of this study are not only beneficial to the educational institutions in India but also to other similar educational institutions in other countries too. The qualitative and quantitative findings help teachers, educational institutions, government and other stakeholders to develop effective policies, strategies, modules, pedagogies etc. to make teaching more suitable to the students with multi style learning. The findings and recommendations of this study can collaborate with the new education policy India 2020 for the grass-roots level of transformation in Indian

education. Developing and underdeveloped countries can also use the findings of this study to set up appropriate teaching learning platforms in educational institutions. Even industries working on information and communication technologies can adopt these findings to develop new machineries which supports better learning to the students with multi style learning and teachers for effective teaching. The newly developed questionnaires included appropriate items to assess the respondent's background, learning style, learning essentials and teaching method, and validated which can be used for further studies in the related research activities

FURTHER SCOPE OF THIS RESEARCH

The present study would be a potential base for further research in the area of teaching-learning with special reference to different age groups, geographical and social settings and educational institutions in other parts of the country and abroad.

CONCLUSION

Understanding student's learning styles and learning essentials are two major parts to create an effective and experiential learning opportunity. In a classroom setting teachers play a key role to facilitate both better learning and development. Unless a teacher understands the need for matching their teaching approach to the student's learning style with appropriate skills, and knowledge these goals may not be achieved. Therefore, to bridge this gap between teaching and learning researcher conducted this study with the main aim of identifying the present method of teaching, learning style, and learning essentials of the students in government schools. Statistical approaches such as Descriptive, Comparison, and Correlation Analysis of the selected variables revealed that a very high significant correlation between auditory, visual, and kinesthetic methods of teaching, learning style, and learning essentials. A majority of the rural students are identified with multi-style learning.

The impact of certain demographic factors such as parent's qualifications and occupation, family income, residential area, etc. are found to be very high in deciding students' academic performance. Highest majority of the students expecting auditory, visual and kinesthetic methods of teaching in their classroom. But it is observed that the poor teaching and learning environment in government secondary schools is a challenge to the teachers to provide an effective learning experience to the students. To achieve the gap between teaching and learning recommendations drawn with the appropriate review of existing research, a systematic observation by the researcher, student's opinion, and the suggestions of various educational professionals. The findings are potential tools

to convert the traditional method of teaching and learning to learning style preferred teaching and learning. The effective contribution by the various stakeholders such as parents, students, teachers, educational institutions, school administrations, department of education, government, and non-government organizations towards teaching and learning in government schools will help the nation to achieve progress and prepare well-qualified citizens.

CHAPTERIZATION

This synopsis is structured with both the following chapters to signify the approach proposed and its verification of the expressions embodied.

The first chapter deals with the backdrop of this study outlining the rationale, objectives, and limitations of the study along with the statement of the problem and research questions for this study.

The second chapter gives an overview of studies related to learning essentials confirming the standpoint and perspective of this synopsis.

The third chapter is devoted to a description, of the research design, methods used, the sample selection, a thorough description of the procedures used to conduct the research, and a description of the tools used for data collection.

The fourth chapter presents the results of the study; through analysis and interpretation of the collected data.

The fifth chapter concludes the dissertation within the discussions of findings, implications of the study, suggestions for further research, and conclusions drawn from this study.

The sixth chapter presents a summary of the entire study.

Bibliography: It includes the references of secondary data, which help in identifying, developing, and solving a research problem.

Annexure: It includes all questionnaires used for data collection in this study.